

**MEASURING ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP
BEHAVIOR OF LECTURERS: THE ROLE OF PERSONALITY
AND LOCUS OF CONTROL**

**Okoye, Chukwuemeka A. F.¹ⁱ,
Ezeh, Leonard N.²,
Mbanugo, C. J.³,
Etodike, C. E.⁴**

^{1,2}Ph.D., Department of Psychology,
Faculty of Social Sciences,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University,
Awka, Nigeria

^{3,4}Department of Psychology,
Faculty of Social Sciences,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University,
Awka, Nigeria

Abstract:

This study examined the influence of personality and work-locus of control on lecturers' organizational citizenship behaviour. A total of 204 participants (75 females and 129 males) selected through simple random sampling technique were drawn from Federal Polytechnics Oko Anambra State, Nigeria as participants of the study. Their ages ranged from 27 to 67 years with a mean age of 49.43 years and a standard deviation of 9.82. A cross sectional survey design was employed for the study while two-way Analysis of variance statistic was used for data analysis. The result revealed a significant main effect for personality at $F(4,194) = 4.15, p < .05$. Extraverted lecturers had more tendencies to practice OCB than open to new experience and agreeable lecturers, as well as conscientious lecturers. However, no significant influence for work locus of control ($M=1,194) = 0.67 > .05$ with the internal locus of control participants ($m = 121.05, SD = 32.77$), was observed on tendency to practice OCB than their external ($M. 121. 64, SD = 25.41$) counterparts. Also, the result showed no significant interaction effect between personality factors and work-locus of control on lecturers' citizenship behaviour, $F(4, 194) = 1.08$ AT $p < .05$. It recommended that Nigerian tertiary institutions use psychometric evaluation in lecturers' selection process in order to take advantage of those more likely to exhibit citizenship behaviour.

ⁱ Correspondence: email nelsonetodike@gmail.com

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1. Introduction

The Nigerian educational system as it is nowadays has moved into an era competitive and complex challenges requiring essentially reorganization of its policies (Miller, 2002). Success of school (tertiary institutions) fundamentally depends on lecturers if they are committed to the goals and values of tertiary education (Oplatka, 2006; Somech & Ron, 2007). Despite so many challenges facing the sector, more lecturers are willing to go above and beyond the call of duty to contribute to successful change; they may have been prompted by citizenship behaviour (Somech, 2007).

In the current study, lecturers' citizenship refers to organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) while personality is contextualized as the big five model. Lecturers' citizenship behaviours refer to those behaviours that are discretionary, which the lecturers are not bound by law to perform, but which will help impart knowledge to the students. Such citizenship behaviour may include: the use of projector during lectures, giving students course outline, and hand-outs to prepare ahead of the lecturers, teaching students broadly and allowing them to jot down things to avoid forgetfulness which could be caused by interference, introducing students to the use of school library and internet facilities, giving home works, seminars, etc.

Bateman and Organ (1983) first coined the words organizational citizenship behaviour so also Smith, Organ and Near (1983). They drew this from the concept of willingness to cooperate as contended by Barnad (1938). According to them, the distinction between dependable role performance and innovation and spontaneous behaviours (Katz, 1964) Katz & Kahn, 1966; 1978) may be citizenship behaviour. Organ (1988) later defined OCB as individual behaviours that is discretionary, not directly and explicitly recognized by the formal reward system and that in the aggregate promotes effective functioning of the organization. By discretionary, it means that the behaviour is not an enforceable requirement of the role or the job description (that is, the clearly specifiable term) of the person's employment contract with the organization. The behaviour is rather a matter of personal choice, such that its omission is not generally understood as punishable. Other related concepts to organizational citizenship behaviour are; extra-role behaviour (Van Dyne, Cummings & Park, 1995), pro-social organizational behaviour (Brief & Motowildo, 1986) George & Bettenhausen, 1990), contextual performance (Borman, Smith & Motowildo, 1997) and organizational spontaneity (George & Brief, 1992; George & Jones, 1997).

Based on leading studies on OCB, any organization with high prevalence rate of OCB is less associated with; turnover, absenteeism, employee dissatisfaction and sabotage (Chen, Hui & Segó, 1998). Presumably therefore, in schools (tertiary institutions) where OCBs are practiced, there will be reduced absenteeism, lecturers' satisfaction and loyalty, improvement in academic performance of students, reduced

unrest and restive behaviour. In the researcher's opinion, greater understanding of OCBs in school settings will make an important contribution toward nurturing school effectiveness. The two dimensions of OCB – altruism (OCBI) and generalized compliance (OCBO) certainly have the potential to enhance the effectiveness of schools in the same way they contribute to other kinds of organization. Unfortunately, it seems school research has neglected the contract.

Schools as organizations can be described in terms of client serving professionals operating in a bureaucratic setting. Theoretically, this bureaucratic setting is incompatible with the needs and expectations of professionals (Dipaola & Morgan, 2001). As teaching became the most unionized profession (Finn, 1985). Theorists and researchers predicted a profound negative impact on school organizations from the presumed "*clash between positional and professional authority*" (Davies, 1974). Teachers' job description include: teaching, administration, research and character building of students to collaborate in the development of school plans, policies and programmes. In fact, "work to rule" is a tactic often employed by teacher unions to punish school settings when contracts have expired or when contract negotiations are at an impasse (Dipaola & Morgan, 2001).

With reference to the part of the definition of OCB which says that OCB has an effect on organizational effectiveness and efficiency; an organization is likely to perform better without extra expenses, if people that are hired are more likely to engage in OCB than others (Organ, 1990b). The success, effectiveness and efficiency of every organization depend mostly on the commitment and organizational behaviour of its employees as human resources is the most important asset to every organizational setting (Ezeh, Etodike & Ike, 2017; Ezeh, 2016).

Personality refers to those biological and environmentally determined characteristics within the person that accounts for distinctive and relatively enduring patterns of thinking, feeling and acting (Passer & Smith, 2001). It has been observed that neuroticism dimension of personality is a negative predictor of citizenship behaviour while conscientiousness, agreeableness, extraversion and openness to new experience are positive predictors of citizenship behaviour. Spector, Jex and Chen (1985) found that individuals high in optimism tend to be in job with high autonomy, skill, variety and task identity. However, Farooqui (2012) discovered that in tertiary institutions, leadership, workplace relationships, organizational system and job characteristics of organizational climate also have significant stronger relationship with OCB. Farooqui (2012) further stated that leadership style may strongly enhance or mar worker performance.

Spector (1998), described work locus of control as a personality variable; a generalized expectancy that rewards or reinforcement outcomes in life are controlled either by one's own action (internality) or other forces (externality). Selecting employees high in openness to experience and internal locus of control can result in higher level of employees OCB performance (Hossan & Hanain, 2010). Spector (1982) noted that individuals with internal locus of control exhibit greater personal career effectiveness,

exert greater effort, perform better on the job and demonstrate greater job satisfaction than externals. It predicts some aspects of OCB such as altruism, courtesy and sportsmanship (Konovsky & Organ, 1996; Podsakoff, Organ & Mackenzie, 2006). Studies also show that individuals with an internal locus of control have more sources of social support available to them (Honsson, Jones & Carpenter, 1984; Jones, 1982). Spector (1982) suggests that cognitive consistency explains why individuals with high internal locus of control tend to be more satisfied with their job – they believe they can choose to leave or stay in a job situation. Individuals who do not feel that they are in control of their environment may actively seek out work on home environments that allow them flexibility and control over their work or family schedules.

However, five factor model also called high-order factors, consists of several of Cattell's sixteen personality factors which opined that when a person is placed at a specific point at each of those five dimensions by means of a psychological test, behaviour ratings or direct observations of behavior, the essence of his/her personality has been captured (McCrae & John, 1992). According to McCrae and Costa (1997), extraversion – is a person's level of sociability and enthusiasm; agreeableness – refers to how friendly, nurturant and caring a person is as opposed to cold, in different, self-centered; conscientiousness are irresponsible, careless and undependable; neuroticism – refers to negative and upsetting emotions and persons who are high in neuroticism tend to be anxious, emotionally sour, irritable and unhappy; openness to experience – persons who have these traits are intelligent and open to new ideas.

In the views of Jahangir, Akbar and Hag (2004), successful organizations have employees who go beyond their job responsibilities and freely give off their time and energy to succeed at the assigned job. It has been observed that the personality of individuals account for why they act positively or negatively to the same situation. Persons who have internal locus of control believe that they can rule their world and so strive towards achieving this in their work environment. On the other hand, those with external locus of control rely on fate to determine their position in their work environment. Therefore, such individuals with internal locus of control can practice OCB and as well encourage others to do the same irrespective of their working condition; whereas those who have external locus of control have difficulties practicing OCB in their workplace (Spector, Cooper, Sanchez, O. Driscoll & Sparks, 2002).

2. Literature

Several theories have been put forward by researchers to explain the concept of organizational citizenship behavior. One of such theories, the self – consistency theory, developed by Korman (1976), states that individuals will engage in behaviours that are consistent with their perceptions in order to maintain a sense of cognitive balance. This theory provides a rationale for why individuals may be motivated to engage in citizenship behavior. Furthermore, the self-determination theory (SDT) is a theory of human motivation and personality; which involves motivation with regards to choices

people make without external influence and interference. It focuses on the degree to which an individual behaviour is self-motivated and self-determined (Deci & Ryan, 2012, Ryan and Deci, 2002; 2017).

Another theory, the social exchange theory, seeks to explain the relations between employees and enterprises. It is the basic concept to understand the employee behaviours in workplace (Cropanzano & Michell, 2005). This relationship may develop into a trust, loyalty and mutual commitment. Its principles include: (1) Reciprocity (2) collective benefits, and (3) identity consistency (Zhu, 2012). The opinion that affective job satisfaction plays an intermediary and conducive role in employees' exchange relationship perception and organizational citizenship behaviour also abound (Zhu, 2012). The theory assumes that the two parties in social exchange must adhere to certain rules of exchange. These rules will become the normative definition of term between the two parties. The basic principle of exchange is reciprocity which is based on trust. The exchange relationship perception of the implicit contract between employees and enterprises is based on social affective benefits and trust.

In the empirical domain, Elanain, (2007) studied the relationship between personality and OCB among 230 employees working in a variety of service organizations in Dubai. The result of hierarchical regression analysis showed that openness to experience, conscientiousness and emotional stability were valid predictors of OCB. However, both extraversion and agreeableness showed no significant relationship with OCB.

Noor (2009) studied organizational citizenship behaviour as the outcome of organizational commitment, using university teachers in Pakistan. The data was collected from 160 university teachers in Pakistan through questionnaire. The result obtained revealed that training and development opportunities, work-life policies, and empowerment practices have significant positive relationship with organizational commitment and also organizational commitment impact positively in enhancing the organizational citizenship behavior of the teachers.

Dipaola and Morgan (2001) studied OCB in schools and its relationship to school climate. The participants were teachers in 97 public schools across Ohio in Williamsburg. The four school climate they measured was collegial leadership, teacher professionalism, academic press and community pleasure. They found that OCB was correlated with the collegial leadership of the principal, and that OCB was related to the level of community pleasure the school was experiencing. They also, found that collegial leader support teacher professionalism by treating teachers as the professionals they are. Therefore, a strong correlation was found between leader professionalism and OCB, and also that where teachers exhibit greater levels of professionalism, they perform more altruistic and organizational helpful behaviours.

Singh and Singh (2009), evaluated personality as a predictor of organizational citizenship behavior among managerial personnel in Banaras Hindu university, India. Participants were 188 male employees of public and private companies. Their job tenures with their organization= ranged from one (1) to thirty six (36) years with a

means tenure of 14.59 years; while their ages ranged from 21 to 60 years with a mean age of 39.44 and standard deviation of 10.45. The results of coefficient of correlation indicates that conscientiousness and extraversion dimensions of personality were found to be significantly positively correlated with five dimensions of OCB (conscientiousness, sportsmanship, civic virtue, courtesy and altruism). Agreeableness dimension of personality was significantly positively correlated with other dimensions of OCB except civic virtue, while neuroticism dimensions of personality was significantly negatively correlated with sportsmanship, courtesy and altruism dimensions of OCB.

Kuma, Bakhshi, and Rani (2009) used big five model to explore the relationship between personality and OCB, using a field sample from India. The participants were 187 doctors working in medical college in North India. Four of the big five factors except neuroticism were valid predictors for OCB. Hierarchical regression analysis of data after controlling for demographic variables indicated that conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism were valid predictors for OCB. However, openness to experience showed no significant relationship with overall measure of OCB. However, the result suggests that individual difference (personality) plays a role in predicting whether an employee would exhibit OCB or not.

In view of the above reviews regarding the importance of OCB in the tertiary education sector pertinent questions arise:

- Will lecturers who are conscientious, open to new experience, agreeable and extraverted practice citizenship behaviour in tertiary institution more than those who are high in neuroticism?
- Will lecturers who have internal locus of control practice citizenship behaviour in tertiary institutions more than those who have external locus of control their work?
- Will there be interaction effect of personality and work locus of control on lecturers' citizenship behaviour?

2. Objectives of the study

The major objective of the study was to examine the influence of personality and work locus of control on lecturers' citizenship behaviour. Therefore, the specific aims of the study are;

1. To examine the influence of conscientiousness, openness to new experience, agreeableness, extraversion and neuroticism on lecturers' citizenship behaviour in tertiary institutions.
2. To examine the influence of internal and external locus of control on lecturers' citizenship behaviour in tertiary institutions.
3. To examine the interaction effect of personality factors and work locus of control on lecturers' citizenship behaviour.

2.1 Hypotheses

The following hypotheses have been itemized to guide the research, they are:

1. Lecturers' citizenship behaviour in tertiary institutions will differ due to differences in personality traits.
2. Lecturers' citizenship behaviour in tertiary institutions will differ due to work-locus of control.
3. There will be an interaction effect between personality traits and work-locus of control.

3. Method

204 lecturers (129 males and 75 females) selected through simple random sampling technique participated in the study. Their ages ranged from 27-67 years, with a mean age of 39.43 years and standard deviation of 9.82. Three sets of instruments: big five personality by John Donahue and Kentle (1991) validated in Nigeria by Umeh (2004); work locus of control scale by Spector (1988); and Organizational citizenship behaviour scale by Fox and Spector (2009) were used for data generation.

The researchers met the lecturers at their different departmental offices and lecture halls and gave them the questionnaire to fill. They were allowed to fill the questionnaire at their own convenience. The questionnaires were collected after one week of issuance and analyzed accordingly. The study employed cross sectional survey design while 2-way analysis of variance statistical tool was used for data analysis.

4. Results

Table 1: Summary table of Mean and Standard deviations for personality and work locus of control on lecturers' citizenship behaviour

Independent Variable	Levels	Means	SD	N
Personality	Extraversion	135.05	33.24	21
	Agreeableness	119.52	33.38	42
	Conscientiousness	118.31	26.73	61
	Neuroticism	100.81	24.85	16
	Openness	126.14	24.53	64
WLOC	External	121.64	25.41	109
	Internal	121.05	32.77	95
	Total	121.37	29.00	204

*=p<.05

Table 2: Summary table two-way ANOVA for personality and work locus of control on lecturers citizenship behaviour (LOC)

Source	Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Personality	13189.87	4	3297.47	4.15	.003
WLOC	532.44	1	532.22	0.67	.414
Personality* WLOC	3450.46	4	862.62	1.08	.365
ERROR	154316.34	194	795.45		
Total	170713.43	203			

The result in the table above showed that a statistically significant difference exists among the dimensions of personality (extraversion, conscientiousness, openness to experience, agreeableness and neuroticism) in the practice of citizenship behaviour among lecturers. Consequently, hypothesis 1 was rejected.

However, no statistically significant difference exists between internal and external locus of control in the practice of citizenship behaviour by lecturers. Therefore, hypothesis 2 was accepted.

Finally, no statistically interaction effect was observed between personality factors and work locus of control on lecturers' citizenship behaviour. Therefore, hypothesis 3 was accepted.

5. Discussion

In this study, data analyzed confirmed that there is significant difference in the practice of citizenship behaviour among lecturers exists among the dimensions of personality; hypothesis I was therefore accepted. The findings of this study is in line with the findings by Evie (2010) who studied the relationship between the Big Five personality and work engagement and found a significant relationship between each of the big five factors, agreeableness, conscientiousness, openness to experience and extraversion whereas neuroticism was the only factor with significant negative relationship with work engagement. However, the works of Sigh and Singh (2014) further proved the finding that personality dimensions may be influencing factors in an organizational environment especially among lecturers in the tertiary institution. They discovered that conscientiousness and extraversion dimensions of personality were significantly and positively had higher OCB than other dimensions especially in the areas of conscientiousness, sportsmanship, civic virtue, courtesy and altruism. Also, agreeableness dimension of personality significantly and positively differed with the rest of other dimensions except in the area of civic virtue. Their findings are equally consistent with the previous findings of Kumar, Bakhshi and Rani (2009) that four of the big five factors except neuroticism positively and significantly correlated with OCB. The empirical supports are also support theoretically by McCrea and Costa (1992) who opined that high agreeable individuals tend to be more considerable, tender and always willing to compromise their interest with others. Also, individuals who are high in extraversion tend to be sociable, assertive, talkative, cheerful, upbeat, naturally energetic, enthusiasm, prefer excitement and stimulation (McCrea et al, 1992).

However, hypothesis II was not confirmed. Although, Rotter (1966) explained theoretically that people who have internal locus of control believe they can control their own fate while those who have external locus of control believe that they do not have control over their fate, this difference was not significant in the current study. This is supported by the work of Spater, Cooper, Sanchez, O'Driscoll and Sparks (2002) who found that the relation of work-locus of control, job satisfaction was consistent across all 24 samples in their study, despite a wide range of cultural differences among them.

Equally, hypothesis III which suggested an interaction effect was not confirmed. Although, the finding of Kuma, Rani and Bakhshi, (2009), discovered that conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism were valid predictors of OCB, while openness to experience showed no significant relationship with overall measure of OCB, there is no consistence in its relationship with locus of control in correlating organizational citizenship behaviour. The result suggested that individual differences (personality) play a role in predicting whether an employee would exhibit OCB or not but do not in consonance with the perception of either internal or external work-locus of control.

5.1 Implication of the Study

Nor's (2009) contention that organizational citizenship behavior is one of the important factors that enhances organizational effectiveness is real. Without committed and loyal employees, it is difficult to compete favourable. One of the important qualities of committed and loyal employees is exhibited through their organizational citizenship behaviour. Their beliefs and convictions about the goals of the organization is a propelling force for them to constantly exceed the demands of their work for the good of the organization. The exhibition of OCB is subjective to each employee as it is significantly influenced by personality inclinations and traits. Consequently, as every organization requires employees who perform above the norm (positive on OCB) there is need for them to take into account the subtle individual difference which might influence OCB behaviours during their recruitment process. The need to make use of psychometric tests to determine more altruist applicants is implicated to increase the chances of employees with higher OCB.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, the importance of organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) cannot be over emphasized which is part of the reasons while the researchers explored personality and work-locus of control as determinants of lecturers' citizenship behaviour. Robust review of literature suggested that personality and work-locus of control are subjective factors unique to each individual employee but may be determinants of OCB in relation to organizational climate. The importance of organizational citizenship behaviour in maintaining organizational effectiveness drove the researchers into search for empirical evidence. After analyzing the data obtained

from the field work, the findings confirmed that whereas personality implicated organizational citizenship behaviour, significant evidence was not found on work-locus of control. It is recommended that organizations promote pro-social behaviours of employees through encouragement and formal or informal appraisals. The organization should also consider traits likely to exhibit organizational citizenship behaviour during recruitment exercise in order to increase the chances of organizational citizenship behaviour and other pro-social behaviour which will increase organizational efficiency and effectiveness.

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